

A Study of Fluorescein Complexes with Rare Earths. Part II.

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Bright red or reddish brown complexes of fluorescein with rare earths are probably polymeric in nature. The magnetic moments are in agreement with the room temperature values calculated from Van Vleck formula but at other temperatures an anomalous behaviour is observed due to either polymeric nature of the complexes and/or to ligand field effects. Electrical conductivity data suggest that these complexes have semi-conducting properties and may be expected to be antiferromagnetic. The solid state conductivity generally decreases with the increase in atomic number of the 4f element.

IN continuation of my report on fluorescein complexes of Copper² I describe in this paper the complexes of Ce(III), La(III), Sm(III), Nd(III) and Pr(III).

Experimental

Preparation of the complexes :

The metal salts were obtained from Atomic Energy Commission, Bombay. Fluorescein was obtained from B.D.H., Poole, England.

La(III)-fluorescein complex : The reddish brown complex was precipitated at pH 6.7 from the interaction of 0.05M La(NO₃)₃ and 0.05M alcoholic solution of fluorescein.

Analysis :

Found : C = 43.93; H = 2.68; La = 26.40. Calc. for La C₂₀O₉H₁₇ : C = 45.25; H = 3.14; La = 26.24.

Ce(III)-fluorescein complex : Dark chocolate coloured complex was precipitated in pH range 6.7-6.9. The method was similar to that given above except 0.03M solutions were used.

Analysis :

Found : C = 45.08; H = 2.42; Ce = 27.66. Calc. for CeC₂₀H₁₇O₉ : C = 45.28; H = 3.02; Ce = 26.43.

Sm(III)-fluorescein complex : Dark red coloured complex was formed in the 6.9 to 7.2 pH range. The method was similar to that given above. The solutions used were 0.06M.

Analysis :

Found : C = 20.98; H = 2.34; Sm = 49.25. Calc. for Sm₁₅C₈₀H₁₁₃O₇₅ : C = 21.15; H = 2.28; Sm = 49.71.

Pr(III)-fluorescein complex : A dull red precipitate was obtained from the interaction of 0.04M Pr(NO₃)₃ and 0.01M alcoholic solution of fluorescein

at 6.8 pH at 60°. The complex obtained was dried at 80°.

Analysis :

Found : C = 23.21; H = 2.26; Pr = 49.48. Calc. for Pr₇C₄₀H₅₁O₃₄ : C = 23.50; H = 2.40; Pr = 48.24

Nd(III)-fluorescein complex : A red complex was precipitated when 0.06M Nd(NO₃)₃ interacted with 0.015M alcoholic solution (95% alcohol) of fluorescein in the pH range 6.7 to 7.2. The precipitate was washed with water-ethanol mixture and dried.

Analysis :

Found : C = 17.06; H = 2.17; Nd = 53.2. Calc. for Nd₅C₂₀H₃₆O₂₄ : C = 17.56; H = 2.48; Nd = 52.16.

Magnetic (room temperature), thermo-magnetic; solution, diffuse and infrared spectral; solution and solid state conductivity and thermal measurements were done as given in Part I of this series of papers.²

Results and Discussion

The La(III)-fluorescein complex was diamagnetic ($\chi_a = -0.364 \times 10^{-6}$ c.g.s., $\chi_M = -196.2 \times 10^{-6}$ c.g.s.). The magnetic data for the remaining four complexes are presented in the form of $[\chi_M^{corr}]^{-1}$ vs T plots (Fig. 1). Table I given below shows the room temperature magnetic moments of the complexes alongside the magnetic moments of Ce⁺³, Sm⁺³, Pr⁺³ and Nd⁺³ calculated according to Van-Vleck¹ formula.

Equation used : (v.v.)

$$\chi_A = \frac{N}{3kT} \sum g^2 \beta^2 J(J+1)(2J+1) \text{Exp} \frac{-E}{RT} /$$
$$(2J+1) \text{Exp} \left(\frac{-E}{kT} \right)$$

The room temperature (30°) magnetic moments of Ce(III), Pr(III), Sm(III) and Nd(III)

Fig. 1

- $\text{Pr}_7\text{C}_{40}\text{H}_{51}\text{O}_{34}$
 △ $\text{Nd}_5\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{36}\text{O}_{24}$ (Scale shifted by 50 units on Y axis)
 □ $\text{CeC}_{20}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_9$
 ◇ $\text{Sm}_{15}\text{C}_{60}\text{H}_{113}\text{O}_{75}$ (Read ordinates in brackets).

are in good agreement (Table 1) with those calculated by Van-Vleck's formula. However, the magnetic susceptibility versus temperature curves

TABLE 1—ROOM TEMPERATURE μ_{eff} VALUES FOR THE RARE EARTH IONS AS OBSERVED AND AS CALCULATED BY V.V. FORMULA

Complex	μ_{eff} (B.M.)	μ_{eff} (B.M.) Van-Vleck
Ce(III) fluorescein	2.48 (299.6°K)	2.56
Sm(III) fluorescein	1.64 (302°K)	1.60
Pr(III) fluorescein	3.42 (302°K)	3.62
Nd(III) fluorescein	3.64 (287°K)	3.68

Fig. 2.

- △ $\text{Sm}_{15}\text{C}_{60}\text{H}_{113}\text{O}_{75}$
 ○ $\text{CeC}_{20}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_9$ (μ_{eff} values in brackets)
 □ $\text{Nd}_5\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{36}\text{O}_{24}$
 ◇ $\text{Pr}_7\text{C}_{40}\text{H}_{51}\text{O}_{34}$ (μ_{eff} values in brackets).

(Fig. 1) for the lanthanide complexes deviate considerably from either Curie or Curie-Weiss behaviour.

For all the four complexes the temperature coefficient of magnetic moment shows a much higher value in the temperature range above room temperature as compared to that observed below the room temperature. The magnetic moments of these rare earth complexes of fluorescein shows a slight upward trend above room temperature (cf. Fig. 2) indicating crystal field splitting of the ground state of the order of the thermal energy kT . Again, due to high concentration of paramagnetic ions in the complexes, as evidenced by the chemical analyses, ligand field effects and exchange forces between neighbouring metal atoms in the complexes may be playing their part.

All the five lanthanide complexes of fluorescein give closely similar infra-red absorption spectra which is an indication that the same type of bonding may be involved in metal-ligand coordination. The data given in Table 2 below gives the details of the bands (wave numbers) and their assignments. The bands observed for the ligand fluorescein have been included for comparison.

TABLE 2—I.R. DATA OF METAL-FLUORESCIEIN COMPLEXES

Flon.	La(III)- flcn.	Ce(III)- flcn.	Sm(III)- flcn.	Pr(III)- flcn.	Nd(III)- flcn.
3000- 3300(b)	3325(b)	3350(b)	3330(b)	3325(s)	3300(b)
1625(sd)	1640(s)	1635(sd)	1625(s)	1630(sd)	1610(sd)
1588(s)	1590(s)	1580(s)	1562(s)	1575(b)	1550(s)
1400(sd)	1465(s)	1453(s)	1450(s)	1448(s)	1430(s)
1300(s)	1390(s)	1390(s)	1400(sd)	1380(s)	1365(s)
1235(s)	1310(sd)	1285(s)	1285(s)	1300(b)	1300(b)
1204(s)	1216(s)	1210(s)	1205(s)	1200(s)	1200(s)
1110(s)	1113(s)	1110(s)	1106(s)	1100(s)	1156(s)
920(b)	925(s)	920(s)	920(s)	915(s)	1096(s)
	858(s)	855(b)	852(b)	848(b)	910(b)
	760(b)	760(b)	760(b)	755(b)	840(b)
	563(w,b)	570(w,b)	595(w,b)	595(w,b)	605(w,b)
	360(w,b)	365(w,b)	375(w,b)	380(w,b)	385(w,b)

The absorption observed at 1235 cm^{-1} and 1625 cm^{-1} in the I.R. spectrum of pure fluorescein is assigned to C-O stretching and the associated carboxyl group. The significant displacement of OH and C-O group frequencies of fluorescein ligand on complex formation suggest the O-H and COO⁻ as the coordinating positions in the ligand molecule. The carboxyl group is involved in the complex formation due to the pH conditions under which the complexes could be easily isolated. The bands at 565 cm^{-1} etc. can be attributed to $\nu\text{ Ln-O}$ stretching while those at 365 cm^{-1} may be due to $\delta\text{ O-Ln-O}$ where Ln is the lanthanide element.

The metal complexes were insoluble in common organic solvents and had hydroxy bridges as indicated weakly in the infrared spectra and also by the thermal data which is discussed elsewhere. A magnetic interaction between neighbouring atoms in a particular complex was shown by magnetic data. All

these data indicate that these bright red coloured complexes are polymeric. That they may be anti-ferromagnetic can be indirectly inferred from the conductivity data in solid state. In this connection the observations made on other polymeric complexes is significant².

The electrical conductivity data of the rare earth complexes are shown as a function of temperatures in Figs. 3 and 4. The values of slopes, activation

Fig. 3.

energies (in eV) and the temperature T_{DCT} at the discontinuities of the plots of $\log \rho$ against reciprocal of the absolute temperatures are given in Table 3.

From the results it is seen that the conductivity generally decreases down the series of complexes of rare earths. It is also observed that E_a increases with the increase in atomic number of rare earth element above the temperature of discontinuity. These variations in ρ and E_a in these series may be attributed either to impurities or to the antiferromagnetic behaviour of these compounds. The activation energy in Pr(III) complex is seen to be higher than in Nd(III) complex presumably because of

Fig. 4.

TABLE 3—ELECTRICAL CONDUCTIVITY DATA OF RARE-EARTH COMPLEXES WITH FLUORESCIN

Compound	Slope $\log \rho$ vs $1/T$ plot	E_a values (eV)	Temp. ($^{\circ}\text{K}$) at which discontinuity is observed: T_{DCT}
Fluorescein (abbreviated as Flcn.)	1.56×10^3	0.31	—
$\text{La Flcn}(\text{OH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$	1.67×10^3	0.33	—
$\text{Ce Flcn}(\text{OH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$	2.11×10^3 ; 1.74×10^3	0.42; 0.35	378
$\text{Pr}_7(\text{Flcn})_2(\text{OH})_{17}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6$	1.77×10^3 ; 1.02×10^3	0.35; 0.20	353
$\text{Nd}_5\text{Flcn}(\text{OH})_{13}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6$	1.4×10^3 ; 0.93×10^3	0.28; 0.18	361.5
$\text{Sm}_{15}(\text{Flcn})_4(\text{OH})_{37}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_{18}$	2.93×10^3 ; 0.86×10^3	0.58; 0.17	351

more complex hydroxy bridging in the former. The breaks in the solid state conductivity curves are observed to run parallel to maximum changes in the $\partial x/\partial T$ of the complexes (Figs. 5, 6, 7). Thus the magnetic transformations are reflected as breaks in the conductivity plots.

Fig. 5.

- (a) Mass-change curve, $\text{LaC}_{20}\text{O}_9\text{H}_{17}$
- (b) Mass-susceptibility curve $\text{LaC}_{20}\text{O}_9\text{H}_{17}$

Since the discontinuities in the conductivity plots can be attributed to either crystallographic or magnetic or dielectric transitions, it is difficult to say which of these factors are actually responsible for

Fig. 6.

- Mass-change curve, $\text{Sm}_{15}\text{C}_{80}\text{H}_{113}\text{O}_{75}$
- ⊙ ... ⊙ Mass-susceptibility Curve $\text{Sm}_{15}\text{C}_{80}\text{H}_{113}\text{O}_{75}$

the observed T_{DCT} in the complexes studied. It is safe to assume that there are some subtle structural changes taking place at the discontinuity temperatures.

Fig. 7.

- Mass-change curve $\text{Pr}_7\text{C}_{440}\text{H}_{51}\text{O}_{34}$
 □ □ □ Mass-susceptibility curve $\text{Pr}_7\text{C}_{440}\text{H}_{51}\text{O}_{34}$
 ——— Mass-change curve $\text{CeC}_{20}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_9$
 ○ ○ ○ Mass-susceptibility curve $\text{CeC}_{20}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_9$

Thermal and the related magnetic data are given in Figs. 5, 6, 7. The magnetic susceptibility curves were obtained by Watt's method³, in that the complex was heated in a nitrogen atmosphere to a fixed elevated temperature, cooled in the inert atmosphere and the magnetic susceptibility of the residue determined on Gouy balance at room temperature. A muffle furnace with a Sunvicdial-regulated-temperature device was used for heating the samples at fixed temperatures where discontinuities in the thermographs were noticed.

The sample mass susceptibilities increased (barring the La(III) complex which was diamagnetic) between

room temperature and 360°. Deaquation observed in the mass loss curve was responsible for the increase in the χ_a values. The elimination of H_2O molecules from the juxta-posed hydroxy bridges seems a possible explanation for the loss of water molecules near about 200°. This process may be akin to olation observed in some metal ammine complexes⁴.

The thermal and the anomalous paramagnetic behaviour of the lanthanide complexes studied in the present investigation point to the existence of hydroxy bridging. The solid-state conductivity studies and the infrared frequency shifting support this conclusion. Polymeric complexes are usually insoluble in normal solvents and this is found so in the lanthanide complexes. The conclusion is inevitable that these complexes are polymeric in nature and it is this property which may be responsible for the E_a values which are in the semiconducting range.

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